

4-plex quantitative glycoproteomics using glycan/protein-stable isotope labeling in cell culture

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Abstract

Alterations in glycoprotein abundance and glycan structures are closely linked to numerous diseases. The quantitative exploration of glycoproteomics is pivotal for biomarker discovery, but comprehensive analysis within biological samples remains challenging due to low abundance, complexity, and lack of universal technology. We developed a multiplex glycoproteomic approach using an LC-ESI-MS platform for direct comparison of glycoproteomic quantitation. Glycopeptides were isotopically labeled during cell culture, achieving high labeling efficiency ($\geq 95\%$) for both glycans and peptides. Quantitation was validated by mixing the same cell line in a 1:1:1:1 ratio, with mathematical correction applied to deconvolute the ratios. This method proved reliable and was applied to a comparative glycoproteomic study of three breast cancer cell lines (HTB22, MDA-MB-231, MDA-MB-231BR) and one brain cancer cell line (CRL-1620), quantifying glycopeptides from three replicates. The expression of glycopeptides was relatively quantified, and up/down-regulation between cell lines was investigated. This approach provided insights into glycosylation microheterogeneity, crucial for breast cancer brain metastasis research. Benefits include eliminating fluctuations from nano electrospray ionization and reducing analysis time, enabling up to 4-plex profiling in a single injection. Metabolic labeling introduced mass differences at the MS1 level, ensuring increased sensitivity and higher resolution for accurate quantitation.

Graphical abstract

